

FAIR-IMPACT: Preparatory questionnaire - Support for National-Level Initiatives

The purpose of this questionnaire is to assess your drivers for coordinating the implementation of the FAIR principles at national level, based on your organisational perimeter.

The questionnaire focuses on two main objectives:

1. Identifying your primary motivations for participating in the programme.
2. Evaluating the progress you have already made towards implementing FAIR principles.

Your responses will help us tailor the support we offer to better meet your team's needs. Additionally, it will give you clarity on the key areas you may want to focus on and enhance while participating in the programme.

We thank you for your responses

The FAIR-IMPACT team

Deadline to complete the questionnaire:

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

General information

2. Q1. What is the name of your country? *

3. **Q2. What is the name of your organisation? ***

4. **Q3. Who is the main contact person (email address)? ***

5. **Q4. What is your position in your organisation? ***

Your drivers

Whether you're working individually or as part of a team, please rank the following drivers based on their relevance to your organisation within the context of this support programme.

If a particular driver is not relevant to you, please feel free to skip it.

6. **Q5. Driver 1: "Our organisation aims to establish a national network around advancing the FAIR principles."**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

1 = r 5 = very important

7. **Q6. Driver 2: "Our organisation aims to involve research communities in the adoption of FAIR principles."**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

1 = r 5 = very important

8. **Q7. Driver 3: "Our organisation aims to demonstrate commitment to the EOSC vision."**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

1 = r 5 = very important

9. **Q8. Driver 4: "Our organisation aims to show commitment to Open Science."**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

1 = r 5 = very important

10. **Q9. Driver 5: " Our organisation aims to demonstrate compliance with funding body requirements for research data management, FAIR data and data sharing. "**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

1 = r 5 = very important

11. **Q10. Driver 6: " Our organisation aims to demonstrate compliance with national level requirements for research data management, FAIR data and data sharing. "**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

1 = 5 = very important

12. **Q11. Driver 7: "Our organisation aims to be a leading entity in our country in research data management, FAIR data and data sharing."**

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

1 = 5 = very important

13. **Q12. Please share any additional motivations or reasons that are driving your participation in this support programme, if applicable.**

Self-assessment checklist

Please evaluate your organisation's current level of national coordination with the FAIR Principles by assigning a score (1 = Low, 2 = Medium, 3 = High). Please use the descriptions and indicators provided to guide your assessment.

14. **Q13. National / Sectoral Strategy for Implementing FAIR Principles**

Please assess whether your organisation has a formal strategy or framework in place specifically aimed at implementing the FAIR principles.

This includes national policies, strategic plans, or coordinated efforts involving key stakeholders to promote and integrate FAIR practices across research and data management.

Mark only one oval.

- Level 1: There is no coherent national strategy or framework for implementing the FAIR principles. Efforts, if any, are sporadic and lack coordination.
- Level 2: There is a nascent or partially developed national strategy to implement the FAIR principles. Some policies and frameworks are in place, but they are not comprehensive or fully operational.
- Level 3: A comprehensive and well-coordinated national strategy to implement the FAIR principles is in place. There is strong policy support, adequate funding, and active engagement with all relevant stakeholders.
- Not relevant according to our perimeter

15. **Q14. National / Sectoral Policy on FAIR Data**

Please evaluate whether there is an official national / sectoral policy or directive in your organisation or field that specifically addresses the principles of FAIR data.

This includes regulations, guidelines, or formal recommendations aimed at ensuring data is FAIR within the national or sectoral context.

Mark only one oval.

- Level 1: There is no national/ sectoral policy on FAIR data for the specific field. Awareness and initiatives are minimal, and data management practices are inconsistent and uncoordinated.
- Level 2: There is an emerging or partially developed national/ sectoral policy on FAIR data for some specific fields. Some guidelines and standards exist, but they are not comprehensive or fully enforced. Coordination and support are uneven.
- Level 3: A comprehensive and well-coordinated national/ sectoral policy for FAIR data is in place. There is strong political support, adequate funding and active engagement with all relevant stakeholders.
- Not relevant according to our perimeter

16. **Q15. Access to Funding for Research Data Management, FAIR Data, and Open Science**

Please assess the availability of financial support in your country or field for initiatives related to Research Data Management (RDM), FAIR data principles, data sharing, and Open Science.

This includes grants, subsidies, or other funding mechanisms that support the implementation and advancement of these practices.

Mark only one oval.

- Level 1: There is little to no targeted funding for Open Science and FAIR principles. Funding initiatives are scarce and there is minimal governmental or institutional support for these efforts.
- Level 2: There is some targeted funding for Open Science and FAIR principles. While funding programmes exist, they are not comprehensive or fully integrated into the national research funding strategy. Efforts are being made to increase support, but gaps remain.
- Level 3: There is comprehensive and well-coordinated targeted funding for Open Science and FAIR principles. Funding programmes are robust, well integrated into the national research funding strategy, and actively support the development and implementation of Open Science and FAIR initiatives.
- Not relevant according to our perimeter

17. **Q16. Structured National/ Sectoral Network for Disseminating Research Data Management, FAIR Data, and Open Science**

Evaluate whether there is a well-organised national network or consortium that actively promotes and supports Research Data Management (RDM), FAIR data principles, data sharing, and Open Science.

This could include professional associations, research consortia, or collaborative platforms that facilitate the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and resources related to these areas.

Mark only one oval.

- Level 1: There is no structured network at national/sectoral level to disseminate the FAIR principles. Efforts are isolated and there is minimal coordination or cooperation between institutions and stakeholders.
- Level 2: There is a developing structured network at national/sectoral level to disseminate the FAIR principles. There is some coordination and cooperation, but the network is not yet fully established or effective. Efforts are underway to establish and strengthen the network.
- Level 3: There is a well-established and structured network at national/sectoral level that effectively disseminates the FAIR principles. The network is comprehensive, well coordinated and actively involves a wide range of institutions and stakeholders.
- Not relevant according to our perimeter

18. **Q17. National / Sectoral Training Strategy for FAIR Principles**

Assess whether your country / sector has a comprehensive training strategy or programme dedicated to educating individuals and organisations about the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.

This could include formal training courses, workshops, online resources, or certification programmes aimed at building expertise and promoting the adoption of FAIR practices across various sectors.

Mark only one oval.

- Level 1: There is no national/sectoral strategy to provide training in FAIR principles. Training efforts are minimal, uncoordinated and sporadic, with little or no support from national agencies.
- Level 2: There is an emerging or partially developed national/sectoral strategy to provide training in the FAIR principles. Some training programmes and initiatives exist, but they are not comprehensive or fully integrated into a national framework. Efforts are underway to improve and expand training opportunities.
- Level 3: There is a comprehensive and well-coordinated national/sectoral strategy for the provision of training in the FAIR principles. The strategy is well integrated into the national framework, with extensive support, resources and commitment from national bodies.
- Not relevant according to our perimeter

19. **Q18. Participation in Reforming Research Evaluation with FAIR Principles**

Assess your efforts to update and improve research evaluation processes by incorporating new indicators, such as those based on FAIR principles.

This includes contributing to discussions, working groups, or policy developments aimed at integrating FAIR criteria into research assessment frameworks to enhance the evaluation of research outputs and data management practices.

Mark only one oval.

- Level 1: There is minimal or no involvement in the reform of research assessment to include indicators related to the FAIR principles. Efforts are fragmented and there is little awareness of or commitment to integrating FAIR principles into assessment frameworks.
- Level 2: There is some involvement in reforming research assessment to include FAIR principles, but efforts are not fully integrated or standardised. There are initial steps to incorporate FAIR indicators, but implementation is uneven across institutions and disciplines.
- Level 3: There is full and proactive participation in the reform of research evaluation, with robust integration of the FAIR principles. Efforts are well coordinated, with clear policies, guidelines and practices that promote FAIR data management and assessment.
- Not relevant according to our perimeter

20. **Q19. National / Sectoral Focal Point for FAIR Principles**

Please assess whether there is a designated national / sectoral focal point or coordinating entity responsible for overseeing and promoting the FAIR principles within your country / scientific field.

This could include a specific organisation, office, or individual tasked with leading efforts, providing guidance, and serving as a central contact for all matters related to the implementation and advancement of FAIR principles at the national / sectoral level.

Mark only one oval.

- Level 1: There is no designated national / sectoral contact point specifically dedicated to the FAIR principles.
- Level 2: There is an emerging or partially developed national / sectoral focal point for the FAIR principles. Efforts are being made to establish coordination and support mechanisms, but these are not yet fully operational or widely recognised.
- Level 3: There is a well-established and effective national / sectoral focal point for the FAIR Principles. Coordination and support mechanisms are robust, ensuring widespread promotion, implementation and support for the FAIR Principles throughout the country.
- Not relevant according to our perimeter

21. **Q20. Dialogue with Research Communities on FAIR Principles**

Evaluate the existence and effectiveness of ongoing discussions and interactions between your organisation and research communities regarding the FAIR principles.

This includes initiatives such as forums, workshops, consultations, or collaborative projects aimed at raising awareness, gathering feedback, and fostering the adoption of FAIR principles within the research community.

Mark only one oval.

- Level 1: There is minimal or no dialogue with research communities on the FAIR principles. There is a lack of engagement and communication with researchers, and little awareness or understanding of the FAIR principles among the research community.
- Level 2: There is some dialogue and initial efforts to engage research communities on FAIR principles, but engagement is not yet fully integrated or consistently pursued. There are steps towards awareness raising and capacity building, but more systematic approaches are needed.
- Level 3: There is a proactive and well-established dialogue with research communities on the FAIR principles. Engagement is robust, with extensive efforts to promote awareness, understanding and adoption of FAIR principles across different research disciplines.
- Not relevant according to our perimeter

22. **Q21. Please describe any actions taken within your organisation to promote the FAIR Principles, with a focus on dissemination at national level**

Your Challenges

23. **Q22. Please select the main challenges you face with regard to the FAIR Principles**

Check all that apply.

- Structuring the implementation process towards FAIR
- Find funding to cover additional costs for FAIR
- To build a network to disseminate the FAIR principles
- To develop training for FAIR
- Building tools and resources for research data management
- Engaging researchers to implement the FAIR principles
- Changing research evaluation processes and promoting the use of FAIR principles
- Align National initiatives with European initiatives

24. **Q23. Please outline the main challenges you face in implementing the FAIR principles in your national/sectoral context.**

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